

ЎЗБЕКИСТОН РЕСПУБЛИКАСИ ҲУҚУҚНИ
МУҲОФАЗА ҚИЛИШ АКАДЕМИЯСИ

ЮРИДИК ФАН ВА ҲУҚУҚНИ ҚЎЛЛАШ АМАЛИЁТИНИНГ ДОЛЗАРБ МАСАЛАЛАРИ

мавзусидаги халқаро илмий-амалий
конференция материаллари

Т Ў П Л А М И

1-ЖИЛД

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С Б О Р Н И К

материалов международной научно-практической
конференции на тему:

АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ ЮРИДИЧЕСКОЙ
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PROCEDURE FOR REVIEWING CIVIL COURT DECISIONS IN THE APPELLATE INSTANCE AND JUDICIAL POWERS

Annotation: *This article highlights the theoretical and practical issues of reviewing civil cases in the appellate instance. It provides a comprehensive analysis of the subjective and objective grounds for the right to file an appeal, the procedural rules of appellate proceedings, and the powers of the appellate court. Special emphasis is placed on the importance of the appellate institution in correcting judicial errors and omissions, ensuring the legality, validity, and fairness of court decisions, and protecting the violated rights and interests of citizens through judicial means. The article also examines the role of the appellate instance within international standards and foreign practice.*

Keywords: *appellate instance; appeal; civil procedural law; review of court decisions; legality; validity; fairness.*

Аннотация: *Ушбу мақолада фуқаролик суд ишларини апелляция инстанциясида қайта кўриб чиқишнинг назарий ва амалий масалалари ёритилган. Мақолада апелляция инстанциясига апелляция шикоятини келтириш ҳуқуқининг субъектив ва объектив асослари, апелляция тартибида иш юритиш қоидалари ҳамда апелляция судининг ваколатлари атрафлича таҳлил қилинган. Апелляция институти судлар томонидан йўл қўйилган хато ва камчиликларни тuzатиш, суд қарорларининг қонунийлиги, асослилиги ва адолатли эканлигини таъминлаш ҳамда фуқароларнинг бузилган ҳуқуқ ва манфаатларини суд орқали ҳимоя қилишда муҳим аҳамиятга эгаллиги алоҳида таъкидланган. Шунингдек, апелляция инстанциясининг халқаро стандартлар ва хорижий амалиётдаги ўрни ҳам кўрсатиб ўтилган.*

Калит сўзлар: *апелляция инстанцияси; апелляция шикоятини; фуқаролик процессуал ҳуқуқ; суд қарорларини қайта кўриш; қонунийлик, асослилик, адолатлилик.*

Аннотация: *В данной статье освещаются теоретические и практические вопросы пересмотра гражданских дел в апелляционной инстанции. В статье всесторонне проанализированы субъективные и объективные основания права на подачу апелляционной жалобы, правила ведения дел в апелляционном порядке, а также полномочия апелляционного суда. Особо подчеркнута важность апелляционного института в исправлении судебных ошибок и упущений, обеспечении законности, обоснованности и справедливости судебных решений, а также в защите нарушенных прав и интересов граждан через суд. Также показано место апелляционной инстанции в международных стандартах и зарубежной практике.*

Ключевые слова: *апелляционная инстанция; апелляционная жалоба; гражданское процессуальное право; пересмотр судебных решений; законность, обоснованность, справедливость.*

In civil procedural law, the appellate instance holds special significance as one of the key mechanisms for protecting individual rights.

Initially, the procedure for conducting appellate review was introduced into Chapter 37 of the Civil Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan (CPC) through Law №163-II dated December 14, 2000, “On Amendments and Additions to the Criminal Procedure Code, Economic Procedure Code, and Civil Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan.”¹ This law established a new institution within the judicial system to guarantee the protection of individuals’ rights and legitimate interests by enabling the reconsideration of civil cases in court.

According to Part Two of Article 55 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, every person is guaranteed the right to protect their rights and freedoms in court and to appeal decisions, actions, and inactions of state bodies and other organizations, as well as their officials, that are contrary to the law.²

Furthermore, the adoption of Presidential Decree № PF-11 of January 16, 2023, “On Additional Measures to Further Expand Access to Justice and Improve the Efficiency of Courts,”³ has served to enhance legislation aimed at creating full opportunities for citizens and entrepreneurs to defend their rights and legitimate interests in court, ensuring the implementation of the principles of adversarial proceedings and equality of the parties, and securing judicial impartiality in practice.

It is important to note that this Decree enabled the appellate or cassation review of cases initially heard by interdistrict, district, and city courts to be conducted in regional and equivalent courts. In addition, the adoption of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 25, 2023, “On Amendments and Additions to the Civil Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan in Connection with the Improvement of the Procedure for Reviewing the Legality, Validity, and Fairness of Court Decisions,”⁴ further strengthened the status of the appellate institution in the Civil Procedure Code.

The aforementioned law introduced a number of amendments and additions aimed at further improving the appellate instance:

Amendments were made to regulate the procedure for filing appeals against non-final decisions and rulings of courts of first instance, including

¹ Ўзбекистон Республикасининг 2000 йил 14 декабрдаги “Ўзбекистон Республикасининг Жиноят-процессуал, хўжалик процессуал ва фуқаролик процессуал кодексларига ўзгартишлар ва қўшимчалар киритиш тўғрисида”ги 163-II-сонли

² Ўзбекистон Республикаси Конституцияси. Қонунчилик маълумотлари миллий базаси, 01.05.2023 й., 03/23/837/0241-сон. / <https://lex.uz/docs/6445145>

³ Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг 2023 йил 16 январдаги “Одил судловга эришиш имкониятларини янада кенгайтириш ва судлар фаолияти самарадорлигини оширишга доир қўшимча чора-тадбирлар тўғрисида”ги ПФ-11-сонли Фармони. Қонунчилик маълумотлари миллий базаси, 18.01.2023 й., 06/23/11/0033-сон / <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/6358976>

⁴ Ўзбекистон Республикасининг 2023 йил 25 декабрдаги “Суд қарорларининг қонунийлиги, асослиги ва адолатлилигини текшириш тартиби такомиллаштирилиши муносабати билан Ўзбекистон Республикасининг Фуқаролик процессуал кодексига ўзгартириш ва қўшимчалар киритиш тўғрисида”ги Қонуни. Қонунчилик маълумотлари миллий базаси, 26.12.2023 й., 03/23/887/0972-сон

provisions for supplementing and amending appeals (or protests), as well as withdrawing appeals and protests;

To provide participants in proceedings with better opportunities to protect their rights and interests, the time limit for filing appeals and protests was extended from 20 days to one month;

The scope of subjects entitled to file an appeal (or protest) was expanded;

The procedure for filing an appeal was simplified;

New norms regulating appellate proceedings were introduced. In particular, these include the procedure for conducting hearings in appellate courts; the list of documents to be attached to an appeal (or protest); the grounds for returning an appeal (or protest); grounds for refusing to accept an appeal (or protest) for consideration; and the legal framework for terminating appellate proceedings;

The powers of the appellate court were expanded.

Through the review of the legality, validity, and fairness of non-final decisions and rulings, the appellate court acts as a higher authority over cases that are outside the jurisdiction of lower courts.

In scholarly sources, the term *appellatio* (from Latin, meaning “appeal” or “petition”) is described as one of the forms of referring non-final decisions of a court of first instance for a substantive review.¹

As noted by K.N.Annenkov in his work “Commentary on the Statute of Civil Judicial Procedure”, the method of appealing in the form of an appellate complaint could only emerge when centralized state power was sufficiently established, enabling the control of the people's court or its replacement with higher judicial bodies. He associates the emergence of this institution with the statehood of Ancient Rome. In the early Republican period, the Roman civil court consisted of two stages: *in jure* and *in judicio*. In the first stage, the parties and a judicial magistrate participated, although the magistrate did not act as a judge. He merely participated in the formal actions carried out by the parties. This process was called *legis actio* and was based on strict formalism.²

Later, procedures such as *restitutio in integrum* emerged, which allowed, in certain cases, the cancellation of decisions. The plaintiff acquired the right to appeal a judgment. Such appeals were referred to as *appellatio*. The appellate institution was fully formed by the end of the 3rd century AD.³

¹ Фуқаролик процессуал ҳуқуқи. Махсус қисм. Олий ўқув юрти талабалари учун дарслик. / Масъул муҳаррир: ю.ф.д. З.Н.Эсонова.-Тошкент: ТДЮИ нашрети, 2013. – Б. 234. Власов А.А. Гражданское процессуальное право. Верховный суд Российской Федерации, Высший Арбитражный Суд Российской Федерации, Российская Академия правосудия. Учебник. –М.: 2003. - 233 с.

² Апелляция в Российском гражданском процессе: история и современность. Курас Т.Л. // Власть. 2015. С. 36-42.

³ Понятие и признаки апелляционного обжалования в гражданском процессуальном законодательстве России и стран англосаксонской правовой семьи. Понимаш Ярослав Игоревич // Вестник ЧелГУ. 2015. №25 (380). С. 15-22.

Other sources trace the origin of the appellate institution to the word *appellare* meaning “to call upon” or “to summon.” Under this procedure, higher courts, based on the complaints of authorized subjects, would review non-final decisions of lower courts during new judicial proceedings on both factual and legal grounds, and issue decisions within the appellate instance.¹

In legal literature, although the appellate instance is recognized as an important mechanism for correcting judicial errors and protecting citizens' rights, scholars have not reached a consensus on its substantive nature. Some of its features are emphasized, while other aspects remain insufficiently examined. This highlights that the appellate institution is closely linked to key legal principles such as the finality of court decisions, the right to appeal, the right to a fair judgment, judicial protection, and the right to access the courts.²

Researchers in this field interpret the appellate institution in various ways, such as:

- an appellate complaint;
- a specific form of appeal;
- a method of oversight over the activities of lower courts;
- a form of judicial review;
- the process of re-examining lower court decisions;
- a stage in the procedure of appealing a court decision.³

Naturally, the submission of an appellate complaint or protest must meet certain legal requirements. For instance, in civil cases, to appeal non-final decisions or rulings of courts of first instance, the parties must not only have the legal authority to do so but must also express the will to initiate such a procedure.

As rightly noted by Kh.Z.Kuchkarov, who conducted research in the field of criminal procedural law, appealing judgments in the appellate procedure, like in cassation or supervisory procedures, is part of the standard mechanisms

¹ Краткий политический словарь. / Под общ. ред. Шишлина Н.В. и Онникова Л.А. – М.: Политиздат, 1978. - С. 21; Большой юридический словарь. / Под ред. Сухарева А.Я., Крутских В.Е. - М.: Инфра-М, 2004. - С. 33.

² Филатова М.А. Европейские стандарты правосудия по гражданским делам и их значение для российской правовой системы // Стандарты справедливого правосудия (международные и национальные практики) / под общ. ред. Т.Г. Морщаковой. М., 2012. С. 29–63.

³ Гражданский процесс России: учебник / под общ. ред. М.А. Викут. М., 2005. С. 214; Гражданский процесс: учебник / под общ. ред. А.Г. Коваленко и др. М., 2008. С. 310; Борисова Е.А. Апелляция в гражданском (арбитражном) процессе. М., 2008.; Ефимова В.В. Арбитражное процессуальное право: учебное пособие. М., 2009. С. 183; Диордиева О.В. Гражданское процессуальное право: учебно-методический комплекс. М., 2008. С. 230; Ярков В.В. Арбитражный процесс: учебник. 4-е доп. изд. М., 2010; Кунина Л.В. Задачи, цели и функции арбитражного апелляционного суда // Современное право. 2008. № 8. С. 59; Смагина Е.С. Теоретические аспекты апелляционного производства по обжалованию решений и определений мировых судей в российском гражданском процессе: дис. ... канд. юрид. наук. Ростов н/Д, 2005. С. 60; Лепехина Н. Рассмотрение дел судами апелляционной инстанции // Судебные известия. 2005. № 3. С. 25; Осокина Г.Л. Гражданский процесс: особенная часть. М., 2007. С. 584; Грибов Н.Д. Правовая природа апелляции в цивилистическом процессе: дис. ... канд. юрид. наук. М., 2016. С. 57–60.

for challenging court decisions. The initiation of appellate proceedings depends on the will of the participants in the process. The court of second instance does not have the right to independently request a case from the court of first instance and initiate appellate review of its decision. The initiative of participants entitled to appeal judgments and rulings is the driving force behind appellate proceedings.¹

At the same time, despite the diversity of approaches and opinions regarding the definition and elements of appeal, the majority of scholars agree that it consists of two fundamental aspects:

- the reconsideration of a court case;
- the review of a non-final judgment or decision of a lower court.²

In this regard, it is important to highlight Article 372¹, paragraph 1, of the Civil Procedure Code (CPC), which stipulates that the review of the legality, validity, and fairness of a court document is conducted on the basis of an appellate complaint or appellate protest filed against a non-final judgment of the court of first instance, as well as on the basis of a private complaint or private protest filed against a non-final ruling of the court of first instance.

According to this provision, the appellate instance reviews non-final judgments or rulings issued by lower courts.

This issue — the interrelation between these procedural actions — has also sparked scholarly debate. For example, some researchers consider the main element of appeal to be the reconsideration of the case, emphasizing the re-evaluation of facts and evidence presented in the first instance³, others, on the contrary, regard the legal assessment of the lower court's decision as the core element of appeal.⁴ Additionally, there are views suggesting that the true essence of the appellate process lies in striking a balance between these two components — reconsideration of the case and legal evaluation of the initial judgment.⁵

B.Kh.Pulatov, in turn, considers the appellate instance as an important means of judicial oversight, emphasizing its role in correcting judicial errors and promoting consistent and uniform judicial practice.⁶

Moreover, in civil procedure, several essential elements are required to initiate the filing of an appellate complaint and the commencement of appellate

¹ Kuchkarov X.Z. Jinoyat ishlarini yuqori instansiya sudlarida qayta ko'rilishini takomillashtirish. / Yuridik fanlar doktori (Doctor of Science) ilmiy darajasini olish uchun tayyorlangan dissertatsiyasi. T. 2024. 95 bet

² Коршунов Ю.А. Апелляционные суды в судебной системе Российской Федерации. / Дисс....к.ю.н., М., 2022. С. 19.

³ Борисова Е.А. Апелляция, кассация, надзор по гражданским делам: учебное пособие. М., 2013. С. 140; Её же. Последовательность обжалования судебных актов в арбитражном и гражданском процессах // Арбитражный и гражданский процесс. 2012. № 8. С. 32.

⁴ Трещева Е. А. Субъекты арбитражного процесса: дис. ... канд. юрид. наук. М., 2009. С. 112, 113.

⁵ Терехова Л.А. Система пересмотра судебных актов в механизме судебной защиты. М., 2007. 320 с.

⁶ Пулатов Б.Х. Назорат қилишнинг муҳим усули. Ҳаёт ва қонун. 2001, № 4. – Б. 40.

proceedings. Sources in civil procedural law highlight that the legal components of filing an appeal include:

- the presence of a subject entitled to file a complaint;
- the existence of an appealable object (decision or ruling);
- compliance with the timeframe for filing the appeal; and
- the proper procedure for exercising the right to appeal.¹

In her research, Z.Kh.Okhunova notes: "...the procedure for filing an appeal is strictly defined by current legislation, and the dissatisfied party must submit an appeal within the prescribed period."²

Thus, based on the above opinions, it can be concluded that the fundamental condition of an appeal is the reconsideration of the case and the legal evaluation of a court decision.

Legal literature also emphasizes that, in order to exercise the right to file an appeal or protest in appellate proceedings, three primary grounds must be present:

Objective grounds: the existence of an object of appeal (a decision or ruling), compliance with the time limits for filing the appeal or protest, and the case's jurisdiction to the appellate court;

Subjective grounds: the presence of a defined group of persons who have the legal right to file an appeal or protest, and the legal and procedural capacity of these individuals or their representatives;

Formal grounds: adherence to the legal requirements regarding the filing and formalization of an appeal or protest.³

Reinforcing these views, we believe that under civil procedural law, there are four essential elements that must be met for a valid appeal or protest to be filed:

The presence of authorized subjects with the right to file an appeal or protest. In this regard, the relevant subjects are specified in Article 383 of the Civil Procedure Code (CPC) of Uzbekistan.

It is important to note that, under the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 12, 2021, "On Amendments and Additions to the Civil Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan in Connection with the Improvement of the Institution of Judicial Review of Court Decisions," the Commissioner for the Protection of the Rights and Legitimate Interests of Business Entities under the

¹ Гражданский процесс: Учебник / Под ред. д.ю.н., проф. А.Г.Коваленко, д.ю.н. проф. А.А.Мохова, д.ю.н., проф. П.М.Филиппова. – М: "ИНФРА-М", 2008. С.261-262

² Охунова З.Х. "То'лиқ апелляция", "to'liq bo'lmagan apellatsiya» – farqi nimada? Oriental Renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences. July 2022. Volum e 2, Issue 7. – В. 448.

³ Борисова Е.А. Апелляция в гражданском (арбитражном) процессе: 3-е изд., перераб. и доп. - М.: Городец, 2008.-С.119.; Караваева Е.В. Вопросы апелляционного производства в гражданском процессе: Дис.... канд. юрид. наук. - Саратов: 2005.-С.71;

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan was granted the right to file an appeal even in disputes not related to business activities.¹

The subjects entitled to file an appellate complaint include the parties to the case — namely, the plaintiff and the defendant — as well as other persons involved in the proceedings, and even those who were not formally involved but whose rights and obligations were affected by the court's decision. In addition, this right is also granted to the Commissioner for the Protection of the Rights and Legitimate Interests of Business Entities under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, prosecutors, legal successors, and legal representatives.

In cases conducted under the claim procedure, the following parties may initiate an appeal:

- the plaintiff, the defendant, and third parties;
- the Commissioner for the Protection of Business Entities' Rights, except in disputes unrelated to business activity.

In cases conducted under the special procedure:

- the applicant, interested parties, and their legal representatives may file appeals.

In cases related to arbitral decisions:

- parties to the arbitration proceedings and their representatives are entitled to file appeals.²

Appeals may also be filed by persons who were not formally involved in the proceedings but whose rights and obligations were determined by the court. Even if these individuals are not mentioned in the court document, if their legal interests are affected, they have the right to appeal. Legal successors of the parties, third persons, or such affected individuals also enjoy the right to file an appeal, provided that a document confirming legal succession is attached.

Legal representatives or attorneys of parties involved in the proceedings may also file an appellate complaint, provided that the power of attorney explicitly authorizes them to do so. Otherwise, the court may reject the complaint or leave it unconsidered.

According to Article 54 of the Civil Procedure Code (CPC), persons assisting in the administration of justice — such as witnesses, experts, specialists, interpreters, custodians of written and material evidence, enforcement observers, and keepers — do not have the right to file an appellate

¹ Ўзбекистон Республикасининг “Суд қарорларини қайта кўриш институти такомиллаштирилиши муносабати билан Ўзбекистон Республикасининг фуқаролик процессуал кодексига ўзгартиш ва қўшимчалар киритиш тўғрисида” 2021 йил 12 январдаги Қонуни / Қонун ҳужжатлари маълумотлари миллий базаси, 13.01.2021 й., 03/21/661/0011-сон. www.lex.uz

² Ўзбекистон Республикаси Олий суди Пленумининг “Судлар томонидан фуқаролик ишларини апелляция тартибида кўриш амалиёти тўғрисида” 2021 йил 20 апрелдаги 14-сонли қарори / www.sud.uz

complaint against decisions of courts of first instance. Therefore, they are not included in the category of subjects authorized to file an appeal.

Secondly, as another essential element, the scope of authority of the subject must be clearly defined. For example, under current civil procedural legislation, prosecutors are authorized to file an appellate protest only in cases where the prosecutor participated in the proceedings, or if an application is made by certain eligible individuals. Similarly, under Article 383 of the CPC, the Commissioner for the Protection of the Rights and Legitimate Interests of Business Entities under the President of Uzbekistan is authorized to file appellate complaints only in civil disputes arising from civil legal relations.

Thirdly, the object of the appeal must also be clearly identified. Specifically, the subject of the appeal must be a non-final judgment, ruling, or decision of the court of first instance in a civil case. A key requirement is that the court decision must not yet have entered into legal force, and the law must allow for its review through an appeal or protest. For example, a court order (summary judgment) cannot be the object of an appellate complaint.

Fourthly, from an objective standpoint, for a civil case to be reviewed in the court of first instance, it must concern civil legal relations, and the nature of the dispute must allow for it to proceed through further stages of judicial review.

When discussing the significance of the appellate instance in civil proceedings, Sh.Shorakhmetov argues that hearing civil cases in appellate courts serves as an additional guarantee for the protection of citizens' violated rights and legitimate interests through the judiciary. He stresses the importance of establishing a clear and dynamic system for filing complaints or protests against non-final decisions of first instance courts, correcting errors and shortcomings made by those courts, and providing an effective mechanism for reviewing decisions and rulings within the appellate instance.¹

R.A.Khusainova emphasizes that appeal is a form of judicial proceeding initiated in the appellate instance court to substantively review a non-final decision (or ruling) of the first instance court in order to determine the legality, validity, and fairness of that decision. This is achieved by examining the legally and factually significant circumstances of the case, with the aim of correcting any judicial errors. She describes appeal as a set of procedural norms within civil procedural law that ensures the proper resolution of civil cases and provides oversight of the activities of first instance courts.²

In our view, appeal is one of the mechanisms that ensures the legality, consistency in the application of legal norms, and the protection of violated

¹ Шорахметов Ш.Ш. Ўзбекистон Республикасининг фуқаролик процессуал ҳуқуқи. Дарслик. - Т.: Адолат, 2007. -384 б.

² Фуқаролик процессуал ҳуқуқи. Махсус қисм. Олий ўқув юрти талабалари учун дарслик. / Масъул муҳаррир: ю.ф.д. З.Н.Эсонова. - Тошкент: ТДЮИ нашрети, 2013. - 235 б.

rights and interests of citizens through the courts, while also serving as a form of judicial supervision.¹

In this context, it is essential to recognize that, in civil procedure, the appellate instance functions as an independent institution, enabling the protection of the rights and legitimate interests of individuals whose rights may have been violated through errors or omissions in non-final court documents issued by first instance courts.

The way these defining features are addressed determines the formulation of the purpose of the appellate institution.

In our opinion, the primary purpose of the appellate institution is to verify the legality, validity, and fairness of non-final decisions and rulings issued by courts of first instance, and to reconsider them, upon complaints (or protests) filed by authorized persons within the legally prescribed timeframes — thereby ensuring the protection of citizens' violated rights and legitimate interests.

The importance of the appellate institution is also emphasized at the international level. It is considered an integral part of international human rights standards. For instance, the Universal Declaration of Human Rights affirms in Article 10 that every individual has the right to a fair and public hearing by an independent and impartial tribunal in the determination of their rights and obligations.² This principle is also reflected in the 1966 International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, particularly in Article 14, which guarantees the right to appeal a judgment in accordance with the law.³

Additionally, this right is reaffirmed in the 1995 Convention of the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS) on Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms, specifically in Article 7, paragraph 2, which ensures the right to judicial appeal procedures in protecting human rights and freedoms.

In addition, norms related to appellate complaints are reflected in the recommendations of the Committee of Ministers of the Council of Europe, as well as in the case law of the European Court of Human Rights (ECHR). The ECHR underscores the importance of the right to appeal, often recognizing it as a necessary prerequisite for bringing a case before this international judicial body.⁴

¹ Шайзаков Ш.И., Қандаҳорова Д.С. Айрим тоифадаги фуқаролик ишлари кўрилишида прокурор иштироки // Илмий амалий қўлланма.- Тошкент, Ўзбекистон Республикаси Бош прокуратураси Академияси, 2022. – 114 б.

² <https://constitution.uz/uz/pages/humanrights>

³ <https://lex.uz/docs/2640479>

⁴ Шугуров М.В. Международно-правовые стандарты и реализация права на апелляцию по уголовным делам в российском уголовном процессе: доктринально-правовая оценка соответствия // Международное уголовное право и международная юстиция. 2009. № 3. С. 8–16.

The Model Code of Civil Procedure, developed for the member states of the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS), also includes specific provisions on appellate complaints.¹

The appellate institution is widely applied in the civil procedural legislation of many countries around the world, including Germany, France, the United Kingdom, Sweden, Austria, and the Netherlands. These jurisdictions demonstrate the global recognition of appeal as a key legal mechanism for ensuring justice and correcting judicial errors.²

For this reason, the appellate instance has become a widely recognized classical method of judicial review around the world.

Thus, the appellate court plays a fundamental role as an independent branch of judicial authority in protecting the rights and legitimate interests of citizens.

According to D.J.Suyunova, “The function of appellate proceedings is multifaceted: it involves correcting errors made by the court of first instance, ensuring compliance with substantive and procedural law, and influencing the formation of lower court practice. Ultimately, its goal is to safeguard the rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests of individuals.”³

Indeed, as the scholar rightly notes, during the review of a non-final judgment by the appellate instance in civil cases, the court verifies compliance with both substantive and procedural law. Based on the results of this review, conducted under Chapter 44 of the Civil Procedure Code (CPC), the appellate court may issue one of the following rulings:

- Leave the judgment, ruling, or decision unchanged;
- Fully or partially annul the judgment, ruling, or decision and issue a new one;

- Fully or partially amend the judgment, ruling, or decision;
- Fully or partially annul the judgment and either leave the claim unconsidered or terminate the proceedings, in accordance with legal grounds;

- If the case was heard in violation of rules on subject-matter jurisdiction, annul the decision and refer the case to a competent court.

When reviewing a private complaint (or protest), the appellate court may:

- Leave the ruling unchanged;
- Annul the ruling and refer the statement of claim (or application) to the first-instance court for substantive review;

¹ О концепции и структуре Модельного кодекса гражданского судопроизводства для государств – участников СНГ // Постановление Межпарламентской Ассамблеи государств – участников СНГ от 16 июня 2003 г. № 21-6. URL: <http://pravo.Levonevsky.org/bazaby/org327/basic/text0083.htm>

² Албегова З.Г. Институт апелляция в арбитражном процессе. Автореф. дисс... канд. юрид. наук. - М., 2008. - С.17.

³ Суюнова Д.Ж. Апелляция инстансияси хорижий тажрибасида. Судлар фаолиятини рақамлаштириш: жорий ва истиқболдаги вазифалар мавзусидаги ўтказилган халқаро илмий-амалий конференция материаллари тўплами // Т.: ТДЮУ, 2022 й. – Б. 181.

Fully or partially amend or annul the ruling and resolve the matter substantively;

Annul the ruling and transfer the statement of claim (or application) to another court based on jurisdictional rules.

The procedure for examining a case in the appellate instance is largely similar to that of the first instance. If a party is dissatisfied with the appellate court's decision, they have the right to file a cassation or supervisory appeal as established by procedural law.

Based on this study and earlier legislative developments aimed at improving the appellate instance, the following theoretical conclusions can be drawn regarding the distinctive characteristics of the appellate institution as an independent branch of civil procedural law:

An appellate complaint (or protest) is filed by an interested party in accordance with the law, directed to a higher court against a non-final judgment or ruling of the first-instance court;

The complaint or protest typically argues that: (a) the facts important to the case were not fully established or proven; (b) the conclusions reached by the court do not align with the circumstances of the case; (c) there were violations or misapplications of substantive or procedural legal norms;

The appellate complaint (or protest) must be filed once, within the period specified by law, starting from the date the decision was announced;

Filing an appeal suspends the legal force of the decision. If the decision is not annulled by the appellate court, it enters into force and is subject to enforcement;

The appellate court may review new arguments and additional materials, even if they were not mentioned in the original complaint or protest;

Cases in the appellate instance are reviewed collegially (by a panel of judges);

The appellate court has the authority to leave the decision unchanged, amend or annul it, adopt a new ruling, or — in cases prescribed by law — review the case as a first-instance court, leave the case unconsidered, or terminate the proceedings.

These principles illustrate the comprehensive powers and crucial role of appellate courts in ensuring legality, fairness, and justice in civil proceedings.

Based on the above, it can be concluded that in the administration of civil justice, the appellate instance functions as an independent institution that enables the protection of the lawfully safeguarded rights and legitimate interests of citizens, the state, and society. It does so by promptly correcting errors and deficiencies found in court decisions issued by first-instance courts that have not yet entered into legal force.

To properly initiate an appellate complaint or protest, four essential elements must be present:

The subject (an authorized party);

The subjective aspect (the party's legal interest and competence);
The object (a non-final court decision or ruling);
The objective aspect (a dispute within civil jurisdiction that allows further judicial review).

This means that the main goal of the appellate institution is to review the legality, validity, and fairness of non-final judgments and rulings issued by courts of first instance, and to correct any identified errors or violations through complaints or protests submitted by authorized parties within the legally prescribed timeframes — ultimately ensuring the protection of violated rights and legitimate interests.

Thus, the appellate instance in civil courts of Uzbekistan represents a mid-level court within the independent judiciary of the Republic. It operates as a body that:

- reconsiders civil cases based on complaints (or protests),
- reviews the legality, validity, and fairness of non-final judgments and rulings,
- verifies the factual circumstances of a case similarly to the court of first instance,
- and has the authority to re-examine final court decisions in light of newly discovered circumstances.

In doing so, the appellate court acts as an independent organ of judicial power dedicated to eliminating material and procedural legal violations and protecting the legally guaranteed rights and interests of citizens, the state, and society.

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PROBLEMS RELATED TO THE USE OF THE PROSECUTOR'S SUBMISSION AND ISSUES OF IMPROVING ITS EFFECTIVENESS

***Abstract.** This article is devoted to problems related to the preparation and application of the prosecutor's submission, as well as ways to improve its effectiveness. The author discusses a number of systemic issues related to the submission, which is the most commonly used supervisory document following the results of the prosecutor's inspections of the execution of laws. The author substantiates these issues with empirical materials studied during the research and the results of a sociological survey. The author provides suggestions for addressing the problems associated with the preparation and application of the prosecutor's submission.*

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Бош илмий котиб

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